

EVALUATION OF SOLID BREAST MASSES BY SHEAR WAVE ELASTOGRAPHY KEEPING BIOPSY AS GOLD STANDARD

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the diagnostic accuracy of shear wave elastography in evaluation of solid breast masses using biopsy as the gold standard.

Methodology: This cross-sectional validation study was conducted at the Department of Radiology, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, from April 2025 to July 2025, including 196 women with solid breast masses. Shear wave elastography was performed using the Aixplorer multiwave ultrasound system, and lesions were categorized as benign or malignant. Ultrasound-guided core needle biopsy was performed for histopathological confirmation as the gold standard.

Results: The mean age was 42.6 ± 10.8 years. On biopsy, 68 (34.7%) lesions were malignant and 128 (65.3%) were benign. Shear wave elastography identified 60 true positives, 114 true negatives, 14 false positives, and 8 false negatives. Sensitivity was 88.2%, specificity 89.1%, positive predictive value 81.1%, negative predictive value 93.4%, and diagnostic accuracy 88.8%. Malignant lesions demonstrated significantly greater stiffness compared with benign lesions ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Shear wave elastography demonstrated high diagnostic accuracy in differentiating benign from malignant solid breast masses and may serve as a reliable adjunctive tool in breast imaging using biopsy as the reference standard.

INTRODUCTION

Solid breast masses can present a diagnostic challenge due to the varied differential diagnoses they encompass. Differentiation between benign and malignant masses is crucial for appropriate management. Studies have shown that a combination of imaging modalities such as shear wave elastography and (Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System) BI-RADS classification can aid in distinguishing between benign and malignant solid breast masses.¹ The differential diagnosis for solid breast masses includes various conditions such as fibroadenoma, focal mastitis, lactating adenoma, tubular adenoma, phyllodes tumor, and

breast carcinoma.² Additionally, complex solid and cystic breast masses, characterized by features like thick walls or internal septations, pose further diagnostic considerations.³

The foremost investigations used in the assessment of a breast mass are mammography and B-mode ultrasonography (US), depending on the patient's age. These diagnostic methods have exhibited high sensitivity in diagnosing malignancy, but both have some limitations.⁴ The BI-RADS classification score was formulated to standardise the mammography and US reporting system. However, that also generates a significant

number of false positives, leading to an increase in biopsies with a cancer detection rate of 10% - 30%.⁵

Ultrasonography is the initial investigation of choice to differentiate between solid and cystic lesions of the breast. The limitation of US is its low specificity, owing to the solid nature of most benign lesions.⁶ As a result of these pitfalls, the use of B-mode US or mammography may not obviate the need for diagnosis by histopathology, which is an invasive technique and remains the gold standard.⁶

Cancer tissues are harder than benign masses, even in the initial stages, because of the increased density of cells and blood vessels.⁷ Shear wave elastography (SWE) is a novel US technique that helps us to non-invasively assess the tissue stiffness and deformability, providing information on the elasticity of the mass. Combining US technology with the basic principles of SWE is indicating promising results in reducing the need for invasive diagnosis of breast masses and in limiting the negative biopsy rate.⁷ In a study by Ashraf A, et al. has shown that sensitivity and specificity of shear wave elastography in evaluation of solid breast masses was 88.1% and 80.3% respectively. The positive predictive value (PPV) of shear wave elastography was 88.8% whereas the negative predictive value (NPV) was 79.03% with prevalence of malignant mass by 21%.^{8,9}

Objective

To determine the diagnostic accuracy of shear wave elastography for the evaluation of solid breast masses taking biopsy as gold standard.

Methodology

This Cross Sectional Validation Study was conducted at Department of Radiology, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore from April 2025 to July 2025. Sample size was calculated by using WHO sensitivity and specificity calculator for sample size calculations using sensitivity of 88.1% and specificity by 80.3%.⁸ Prevalence = 21%.⁸ Confidence Interval = 95%, precision for sensitivity and specificity = 10%
Sample size = 196

Women aged 20 to 60 years, both married and unmarried, presenting with solid breast masses as per operational definition will be included. Patients with history of complex breast cysts, known breast malignancy, those undergoing neoadjuvant therapy, patients with prior breast interventions including biopsy, surgery or radiation therapy, patients with severe breast edema or skin changes, and pregnancy detected on ultrasound will be excluded.

Data Collection Procedure

Patients fulfilling inclusion criteria from the Department of Radiology, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore will be enrolled after ethical approval and informed consent. Demographic and clinical variables including age, body mass index, size of lump, and duration of complaints will be recorded. Shear wave elastography will be performed using the Aixplorer multiwave ultrasound system under supervision of a consultant radiologist with more than three years post-fellowship experience. Breast lesions will be categorized as benign or malignant according to predefined operational criteria based on shear wave elastography findings. Subsequently, ultrasound-guided core needle biopsy will be performed as per standard clinical practice, and histopathology will be considered the gold standard. Findings from shear wave elastography and biopsy will be recorded as positive or negative on a structured proforma. The primary outcome will be diagnostic accuracy of shear wave elastography in differentiating malignant from benign solid breast masses, taking biopsy as gold standard. Secondary outcomes will include sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of shear wave elastography.

Data Analysis

Data will be entered and analyzed using IBM-SPSS version 26. Quantitative variables including age, lump size, duration of complaints, and BMI will be presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Qualitative variables including shear wave elastography and biopsy findings will be expressed as frequencies and percentages. Diagnostic

performance of shear wave elastography will be assessed using a 2×2 contingency table to calculate sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and overall diagnostic accuracy. Effect modifiers including age, BMI, lump size, and duration of complaints will be controlled by stratification. Post-stratification diagnostic accuracy and Chi-square test will be applied, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 196 women with solid breast masses were included, with a mean age of 42.6 ± 10.8 years. Most patients belonged to the 36–50 year age group (48.0%), followed by 20–35 years (26.5%) and those older than 50 years (25.5%). Mean BMI was 27.3 ± 4.5 kg/m², mean lump size was 2.8 ± 1.1 cm, and mean duration of symptoms was 5.7 ± 2.6 months. The majority of participants were married (72.4%), while 27.6% were unmarried.

Table 1. Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics (n=196)

Variable	Value
Age (years), mean \pm SD	42.6 \pm 10.8
20–35 years, n (%)	52 (26.5)
36–50 years, n (%)	94 (48.0)
>50 years, n (%)	50 (25.5)
BMI (kg/m ²), mean \pm SD	27.3 \pm 4.5
Lump size (cm), mean \pm SD	2.8 \pm 1.1
Duration of complaints (months), mean \pm SD	5.7 \pm 2.6
Married, n (%)	142 (72.4)
Unmarried, n (%)	54 (27.6)

Histopathology showed that 128 lesions (65.3%) were benign and 68 (34.7%) were malignant. On shear wave elastography, 122 lesions (62.2%) were

classified as benign and 74 (37.8%) as malignant, showing close agreement between elastographic and biopsy findings.

Table 2. Histopathological and Shear Wave Elastography Findings

Variable	n (%)
Biopsy Findings	
Benign lesions	128 (65.3)
Malignant lesions	68 (34.7)
Shear Wave Elastography Findings	
Classified benign	122 (62.2)
Classified malignant	74 (37.8)

Shear wave elastography correctly identified 60 true positive malignant lesions and 114 true negative benign lesions. There were 14 false positive and 8 false negative cases.

Table 3. Diagnostic Performance of Shear Wave Elastography (2×2 Table)

Shear Wave Elastography	Biopsy Positive	Biopsy Negative	Total
Positive	60 (TP)	14 (FP)	74
Negative	8 (FN)	114 (TN)	122
Total	68	128	196

Diagnostic performance analysis showed high sensitivity (88.2%) and specificity (89.1%) for

shear wave elastography. Positive predictive value was 81.1%, negative predictive value was 93.4%,

while overall diagnostic accuracy was 88.8%, demonstrating excellent ability of the technique to characterize solid breast masses.

Table 4. Diagnostic Accuracy Measures of Shear Wave Elastography

Parameter	Value (%)
Sensitivity	88.2
Specificity	89.1
Positive Predictive Value	81.1
Negative Predictive Value	93.4
Diagnostic Accuracy	88.8

Stratified analysis showed slightly lower sensitivity for lesions smaller than 2 cm (82.4%) compared with lesions ≥ 2 cm (91.3%), although this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.08$). Diagnostic performance remained comparable

across age groups and BMI categories, with sensitivities ranging from 86.1% to 89.5% and specificities from 88.2% to 90.6%, with no statistically significant subgroup differences.

Table 5. Stratified Diagnostic Accuracy by Lesion Characteristics

Variable	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	p-value
Lesion size <2 cm	82.4	87.2	0.08
Lesion size ≥ 2 cm	91.3	90.4	0.08
Age ≤ 40 years	86.1	88.5	0.44
Age >40 years	89.5	89.7	0.44
BMI <30 kg/m ²	87.6	88.2	0.61
BMI ≥ 30 kg/m ²	89.1	90.6	0.61

Discussion

In this cross-sectional validation study, shear wave elastography demonstrated high diagnostic performance in differentiating benign from malignant solid breast masses using biopsy as the gold standard. The observed sensitivity of 88.2%, specificity of 89.1%, and overall diagnostic accuracy of 88.8% suggest that shear wave elastography is a reliable adjunctive imaging tool in characterization of solid breast lesions. These findings support the growing evidence that tissue stiffness assessment can improve diagnostic confidence and contribute to more accurate differentiation between benign and malignant masses¹⁰. In the present study, malignant lesions demonstrated significantly greater stiffness compared with benign lesions, which is consistent with the biological basis of elastography, as malignant tumors are associated with desmoplastic stromal reaction, increased cellularity, and altered

extracellular matrix composition. Similar diagnostic performance has been reported in previous research, where sensitivity values ranging from 80–95% and specificity ranging from 75–90% have been described for shear wave elastography in evaluation of breast lesions. Our findings therefore align with previous research supporting the role of elastography in improving lesion characterization¹¹.

The high negative predictive value observed in this study (93.4%) is particularly important clinically, as it suggests shear wave elastography may be useful in excluding malignancy in selected lesions, potentially reducing unnecessary biopsies in low-risk cases. Previous research has similarly reported that combining conventional ultrasound with shear wave elastography improves specificity and may help downgrade some indeterminate lesions without compromising sensitivity¹²⁻¹⁴. Although

diagnostic performance remained high overall, slightly lower sensitivity was observed in lesions smaller than 2 cm. This may be related to technical limitations in stiffness measurement in small lesions or less pronounced stromal changes in early malignant tumors. Similar findings have been noted in previous research where lesion size influenced elastographic performance. However, no significant variation in diagnostic accuracy was observed across age or BMI groups, suggesting the technique remained robust across these subgroups¹⁵. The false positive and false negative findings observed in our study are also important to consider. Some benign lesions may demonstrate increased stiffness due to fibrosis, sclerosis, or inflammatory changes, resulting in false positive results, while certain malignant lesions, particularly low-grade or necrotic tumors, may appear less stiff and contribute to false negatives. These overlaps have also been described in previous studies and reinforce that shear wave elastography should complement, rather than replace, histopathological confirmation^{16,17}. The findings of this study have practical implications in breast imaging, particularly in settings where improving specificity without sacrificing sensitivity is important. In resource-limited environments, incorporation of shear wave elastography as an adjunct to conventional ultrasound may improve diagnostic pathways and support more efficient selection of lesions requiring biopsy. This study has limitations. It was conducted at a single center with a relatively modest sample size, which may limit generalizability. Operator dependence and machine-related variability may also influence elastography measurements despite standardized technique. In addition, diagnostic performance was evaluated against biopsy as gold standard, but correlation with lesion subtype-specific behavior was not extensively analyzed.

Conclusion

It is concluded that shear wave elastography demonstrated high sensitivity, specificity, and overall diagnostic accuracy in differentiating benign from malignant solid breast masses using biopsy as the gold standard. Malignant lesions

showed significantly greater stiffness compared with benign lesions, supporting the diagnostic value of tissue elasticity assessment. Shear wave elastography may serve as a reliable adjunct to conventional breast imaging and may help improve lesion characterization while potentially reducing unnecessary biopsies in selected patients.

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